

Implications of the Adoption of Social Media Platform on Marketing Strategy of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMES) Kano State in Nigeria

AUTHOR: SALEH MUSA SA'AD
 STUDENT NO: 0919387001425 Course 5
 SECURITY AND STRATEGIC STUDIES
 NASSARAWA STATE UNIVERSITY KEFFI
 SECURITY AND DEVELOPMENTAL STUDIES
 SCHOOL OF POSTGRADUATE STUDIES
 NASSARAWA STATE, NIGERIA

CO AUTHOR: FIDELIA MSURSHIMA TILLEY-GYADO
 STUDENT NO: 0919387006914 Course 5

Abstract:- The purpose of this study was to investigate the impact of social media adoption on the marketing strategy of small and medium-sized firms (SMEs) in Kano State, Nigeria. A cross-sectional survey research design is used in this study. The population consisted of 1,794,358 small and medium-sized businesses, and the Taro Yamane method yielded a sample size of 401. For data gathering, a standardized questionnaire was used. Multiple regression analysis was used to analyze the data. According to the findings, the Facebook platform has a substantial impact on the marketing strategies of SMEs in Kano State. Furthermore, the findings revealed that the Twitter platform has a major impact on the marketing strategy of Kano State SMEs. On the contrary, the YouTube platform has a negligible positive impact on the marketing strategy of Kano State SMEs. The study recommends that the management of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in the state of Kano should incorporate social media platforms like Facebook and Twitter into their marketing strategies and use these platforms extensively when providing customer service. As a result, their output will be enhanced.

Keywords:- Social Media, Face Book, Twitter, You Tube, Marketing Strategy

I. INTRODUCTION

It is common knowledge and obvious that in the modern world, in which information and the internet play a significant role in people's lives, the phenomenon of social media will be an interesting topic to research, as will its influence on various marketing strategies. Social media is online content made by the public and made available to end users. It is quickly evolving into one of the most important channels for communicating information to consumers. This phenomena is of considerable importance to marketers since social media is becoming a major source of information exchange, awareness, support, and empowerment of customers (Ahmad, et al 2018).

Despite the fact that the social media arena is continually expanding with more individuals on Facebook, Twitter, and YouTube, most corporate companies, especially SMEs, desire to establish a social presence on these platforms. According to Shelley Walsh's blog on Social Media Statistics (2022), Facebook has 2.9 billion total users, Twitter has 217 million users, LinkedIn has 250 million users, WhatsApp has 2 billion, and TikTok has 1 billion. Many marketers use social media platforms to promote sales, but some business owners lack the knowledge and technological ability to adopt social media marketing techniques (Ntalianis et al 2015).

Additionally, an astonishing number of small enterprises fail. This may be explained by the fact that few small business owners employ social media platforms as a marketing tactic to boost revenue and profitability (Ntalianis et al 2015). Since Facebook and Twitter were first introduced, an increasing number of for-profit companies have included them into their marketing plans. They appear to have realized the social media's potential for fostering consumer relationships and boosting product sales. Since social media is a relatively new type of advertising and is still developing in Nigeria, it is unclear what proportion of users, business owners, and organizations in Kano state are aware of them and using them for marketing campaigns. In light of the foregoing, an investigation into how social media platforms affect marketing tactics in Kano state is being made. It is against the backdrop that this attempt to investigate the impact of social media platforms on marketing strategies in kano state.

However, in both developed and developing economies, a number of studies have attempted to determine the link between the use of social media and the performance of businesses, with mixed results (e.g. Mari, 2016; Bilgin, 2018; Daniel, 2018; Akbar & zgül, 2018; Enenifa & Akintokunbo, 2018; Masa'deh et al. 2021; Tajvidi & Karami, 2021). However, few studies examined the relationship between social media and marketing in kano state. In other words, little has been done with regard to examining the relationship between social media platform and marketing strategies in

kano state. This identified gap informed the need to study the relationship between social media platform and marketing strategies in the context of SMEs in Kano state. This work makes two contributions. First, it adds to the literature on social media and marketing strategy in Kano state, Nigeria . Second, this study's findings will help policymakers comprehend the role of social media marketing for SMEs. The following null hypothesis is provided to address the research problem and achieve the study's objective:

Ho1: Facebook has no significant impact on the marketing strategies of Kano State's small and medium-sized businesses.

Ho2: Twitter has no significant impact on the marketing strategies of Kano State's small and medium-sized businesses.

Ho3: YouTube has no significant impact on the marketing strategy of Kano State's small and medium enterprises.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

➤ Concept of Social Media Adoption

Social media is a relatively recent phrase that has emerged to describe many internet communication channels (Weller, 2015). Overall, social media is defined as "any technology that allows the distribution and sharing of information over the Internet" (Young, et al 2018). Social media, according to Kaplan and Haenlein (2010), is "a series of Internet-based apps that expand on the conceptual and technological foundations of Web 2.0, and allow the creation and exchange of user-generated content." According to Sinclair and Vogus (2011, 294), "social media is a wide word that encompasses software tools that create user-generated content that can be shared." Social media has progressed beyond simply allowing people to communicate with their family and friends. It is now a resource for customers to learn more about their favorite firms and the products they provide (Paquette, 2013). According to Zeeshain and Hussain (2017), social media is the use of web-based and mobile technologies to generate, exchange, and consume information and knowledge across geographical, social, political, and demographic borders via participatory and collaborative public interaction.

• Facebook Adoption

Facebook was founded in 2004 and currently has over 2.9 billion active members (as of May 2022), with 1.9 million users accessing the site via mobile devices. A typical Facebook user has at least 130 friends and is connected to 80 community sites, organizations, and events. Facebook has become into the most effective marketing tool available today. In April 2011, the firm announced a new service for marketers and creative agencies interested in building brand promotions on Facebook. This service is a type of web platform (Portal) that allows marketers and creative design companies to develop brand promotions on Facebook. A Facebook page, according to Nouri and Lorenzo-Dus, (2019), is a place where one can publish the business name, address, and contact information, as well as briefly describe products and services. The business owner can also discuss employees, history, or any other part of the business that is likely to pique the curiosity of other Facebook users and

generate interest in what the firm is doing. In addition to allowing the business operator to submit text, Facebook allows the business operator to upload photographs and videos. This can be an effective method of communicating with clients and potential customers because it allows them to see your goods or service without having to visit your location (Cripps et al 2020).

• Twitter Adoption

Jack Dorsey was the one who came up with the idea for Twitter in March of 2006, and he released it in July of the same year. When using Twitter, as opposed to Facebook, where users can have friends with whom they can discuss a variety of topics, users are required to get connected to the most recent information on topics that they find fascinating. One needs to identify the public stream that most piques their attention and then participate in the dialogues happening there. The standard length for a tweet is 140 characters. It is possible to continue to follow the tweets even if one does not tweet at all, and there is no restriction on the number of tweets that can be sent in a single day. (<http://twitter.com/about>, 2022). According to Hennig (2019), the use of Twitter for the purpose of advertising a company's goods and services is a novel and innovative approach. Over ninety-three percent of marketers make use of social media for professional purposes. It enables companies to give off the impression that they are hip and current while also allowing them to communicate with customers who are interested in their product. Instant exposure can be achieved for a company or its product if a famous person or an influential person tweets about it or uses the product's hashtag on social media, which can lead to an increase in sales. In this day and age, making use of Twitter for professional purposes is a smart business technique that every company ought to adopt (Hennig, 2019). Twitter is quickly becoming one of the most essential platforms for conversation as well as internet connection. According to Holbrook (2016), Twitter has over 8 million unique visitors each month, and approximately 500 million messages are posted each and every day.

• YouTube Adoption

YouTube is a website that was launched in February of 2005 with the purpose of allowing people to publish, view, and share videos with one another with the purpose of providing others across the world with information and inspiration. Displaying a wide range of user-generated video content makes use of both Adobe Flash Video and HTML5 technology, which are utilized by the organization. YouTube serves as a platform for the distribution of material not just by content creators but also by advertising. Every single day, more than 3 billion videos are watched, and mobile devices account for more than 400 million of those daily views (2011). It is estimated that over 800 million individuals use YouTube each month to view videos and upload their own creations. (<youtube.com>, 2022)

➤ Concept of Marketing Strategy

Marketing strategy is the business's marketing philosophy for achieving its goals. Marketing strategy is a company's approach to differentiate itself from competitors and better meet client needs in a given environment (Jain,

2004). Marketing strategies are a series of actions meant to achieve competitive advantage and better-than-average results through intelligent, fact-based selection (Shane, 2000). Marketing strategy definitions incorporate several perspectives (Li and Calantone, 2000). Marketing strategy allows a business to use its resources to achieve its goals and objectives. Marketing strategy is the effective allocation of resources to obtain competitive advantage in a particular market. Goi (2005) defined marketing strategy as a set of tools organizations use to pursue marketing goals in the target market (Osuaagwu, 2006). Marketing strategy establishes the nature, strength, direction, and interaction between marketing mix-elements and external factors in a given situation. According to (Owomoyela, et al, 2013), a company's marketing strategy should generate, build, defend, and sustain its competitive edge. Strategic marketing ambiguity and uncertainty require manager judgment.

➤ *Empirical Review*

Chanthinok et al. (2015) examine the association between social media marketing approach and marketing results. 298 Thai e-commerce enterprises submitted surveys. Hypotheses were tested using regression. Market reaction timeliness orientation has the most favorable impact on all marketing outcomes.

Zulqurnain et al. (2016) studied social media marketing's impact on customer product perception. 152 questionnaires were sent to university students, and 145 (97%) responded. Multiple linear regression analysis was utilized to measure the influence of social media marketing on consumer perception. Social media marketing affects consumer perception, according to the research.

Ahmad et al. (2018) study social media's impact on firm performance in the UK hotel industry. Data analysis in this study used structural equation modeling. 384 UK hotels were surveyed by mail. The data analysis shows a positive association between social media use and corporate performance.

Etim et al. (2018) investigated the connection between the use of social media and the success of businesses in the Nigerian telecommunications industry. From a population of 95 employees at four different telecommunication outlets operating in Rivers State, Nigeria, a sample size of 76 people was determined to be appropriate for the study. This population included customer service personnel, supervisors, and managers. In order to conduct an analysis of the information obtained with the assistance of version 22 of the Statistical Package for Social Sciences software, the statistical method known as the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was utilized. According to the findings of the study, the use of social media has a substantial positive link with performance measurements such as market share and profitability.

Onu and Modupe (2018) conducted research to determine the effect that social media marketing tools have on the success of fashion designing in Abuja. Data was collected through the use of a questionnaire from 132 selected fashion designers in Abuja, out of a total of 897 registered

clothes fashion designers. The secondary data came from a variety of sources, including the internet, periodicals, textbooks, and books. In order to verify the hypothesis, the data were subjected to parametric analysis, and then multiple regression was performed on the data. According to the findings of the study, the overall performance of fashion designers in Abuja was significantly impacted by Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram.

Uwineza, (2019) explored if using social media as a marketing strategy increases marketing efficacy in Century Bottling Company Limited and Crown Bottling Company Limited (Pepsi), both in Kampala. A cross-sectional design was adopted in this investigation. The data was analyzed using frequency and percentage tables, mean and standard deviations, linear regression, and multiple regression. The findings revealed that the platforms Facebook and Twitter have a major impact on marketing performance.

Abdelazeem (2019) looked at how Facebook marketing affects brand engagement among smartphone users in Egypt. to meet the goals of the study, an ex-post facto design was used. A questionnaire has been made, and 502 people who use smartphones have been asked to fill it out. Results showed that marketing on Facebook has a big effect on brand engagement.

Sufian et al. (2020) investigated the impact of social media marketing on online small company sales in Malacca. Explanatory surveys were used to acquire primary data. The sample includes of 150 online small company owners who have had or have not had experiences with adopting social media marketing on their Malacca-based firm. Multiple Regression is used in the requirement analysis test. According to the findings of the study, social media has a direct impact on sales success.

Cripps et al. (2020) study the usage of Twitter in business for knowledge sharing and crowdsourcing information to boost innovation and develop company partnerships in business-to-business marketing. This study uses 52 face-to-face interviews in five countries and downloaded Twitter posts to collect data. Tweets were analyzed using STM and compared to interview data. This approach triangulated between stated and real Twitter use. Twitter helps businesses build significant collaborations by exchanging new, expert, and high-quality information in real time.

Masa'deh et al. (2021) studied the effect of Social Media Activities on brand equity. A cross-sectional quantitative study was carried out utilizing a validated questionnaire distributed to a convenience sample of 362 persons who used one or more types of social media for an airline. A multiple regression analysis was carried out. The findings demonstrated that social media activities had a considerable beneficial impact on brand equity.

Muangmee, (2021) conducted research into the ways in which start-up companies sell their wares and services on Facebook in order to strengthen customer loyalty and support

continued business expansion. SmartPLS conducted an analysis of survey data collected from 225 start-up companies in the food and fashion industries. The findings indicate that the advertising campaign on Facebook has a major effect on the growth and loyalty of the brand.

➤ *Theoretical Framework*

Prahalad and Ramaswamy came up with the Social Media Engagement (SME) theory (2004). The theory says that a user's social interactions with other users lead to a higher level of engagement, which in turn leads to more use of the social media platform. The SME Theory explains how technology works as the foundation for social interactions between users who are in different places and at different times. A big reason for the rise of social media is how technology has changed to give users a unique experience and make it possible for them to connect in ways that were never possible before. The user experience that this research talks about is based on the idea that experience is what you see or do directly at an event. When experience is used as a noun, it means the content that comes from direct participation. When it comes to social media, the user experience is made up of two important parts: the social interactions and the technical features. Social interactions are the way people talk to each other on social media (Prahalad & Ramaswamy, 2004).

Elihu Katz, Jay Blumler, and Michael Gurevitch came up with the Uses and Gratification Theory in 1974. "The theory was made to explain why people don't just sit around and wait for media messages to come to them, but instead actively seek out content that gives them information they need, like, and can use" (Kur, 2003:34). The uses and pleasures perspective looks at media from the point of view of the person who uses it. It looks at how people use the media and what they want to get out of it, as well as what they get out of it. Uses and pleasures: Researchers assume that people know why they watch or listen to different kinds of media and can explain why (Wimmer and Dominick 2003: 403). So, when applied to this study, social media makes it possible for people to take part because it lets advertisers and customers talk to each other one-on-one. The implication is that businesses or entrepreneurs who use social media are active because they make their own Facebook page or Twitter account on their own. Business groups choose social media over other ways to get what they want and reach their goals. The business organization or entrepreneur creates a Facebook or Twitter account for a specific reason. That is, promoting a product or service means connecting with customers.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The design of this study is a cross-sectional survey. It was chosen because it is a way to find out how social media platforms change marketing strategies over time. A questionnaire was also made as a way to collect information for this study. As of 2020, there were 1,794,358 small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs) in Kano State that were part of the study. The owner and/or manager were selected because of their knowledge and familiarity with the running of their establishment. Using the Taro Yamane formula, the sample size was set at 401. (1967). Multiple regression was

used to figure out how to look at the data for this study. This is how the model looks:

$$MKTS = \beta_0 + \beta_1 FB_i + \beta_2 TWT_i + \beta_3 YT_i + \epsilon_i$$

Where:

MKTS= Market Strategy

FB= Facebook

TWT= Twitter

YT= You tube

B0 is constant $\beta_1 - \beta_3$ is the coefficient of the parameter estimate.

ϵ is the error term.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

In this section, the outcomes of the research are given and discussed in light of the findings from the previous sections. Following the presentation of the correlational matrix, the regression findings are shown in their respective order.

Table 1: Correlation Matrix Table

Variable	MKTS	FB	TWT	YT
MKTS	1.0000			
FB	0.2404	1.0000		
TWT	0.1336	-0.0339	1.0000	
YT	0.2147	0.0282	0.0441	1.0000

Source: Output of data analysis using STATA 13

In the preceding section, Table 1 is a correlation matrix table, which illustrates the relationship that exists between all of the different variable combinations used in the regression model. The findings indicate that there is a favorable association between the marketing efficacy of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in the state of Kano and the use of platforms like as Facebook, Twitter, and YouTube. There is a positive connection between all different sets of independent variables, which suggests that multicollinearity should be investigated further. The test for multicollinearity, which makes use of the variance inflation factor (VIF), finds that it is not present because all of the components are less than 10 and the tolerance values are more than 1.0. In table 2, the mean value of the VIF is 1.19. In addition, the diagnostic statistics that were derived from the heteroskedasticity test suggest that the regression model is functioning appropriately (see table 3).

Table 2: Result of Multicollinearity Test

Variable	VIF	1/VIF
FB	1.41	0.708293
TWT	1.34	0.745589
YT	1.04	0.963293
Mean VIF	1.19	

Source: Output of data analysis using STATA 13

Table 3 Heteroskedasticity Test

chi2(1) = 0.60	Prob > chi2 = 0.9578
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Table 4: Summary of Regression Result

	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t
_cons	.1328395	.1898195	0.70	0.484
FB	.6644197	.2271884	2.92	0.004
TWT	.127917	.017717	7.22	0.000
YT	.2411195	.2893971	0.83	0.405
R-squared = 0.2662				
F(7, 432) = 22.38				
Prob > F = 0.0000				

The results of the regression analysis are presented in Table 4. It appears that Facebook and Twitter are significant at the 5 percent level of significance, however YouTube is deemed to be negligible at this level of significance. Consequently, the estimation for the model is as follows: $MKTS = 1328395i + \beta.6644197i + .127917i + .2411195i + \epsilon$

The level of the explanatory factors' contribution to the overall understanding of the dependent variable was indicated by the R-square value. The results of Table 4 show that the R-square value is 0.2662. This indicates that the factors pertaining to social media in the study were responsible for explaining the marketing strategy (MKTS) to the tune of 27 percent. The likelihood of chi2 being 0.000 is equivalent to the value of the F statistic, which is 22.38. The fact that the likelihood of chi2 is significant when set at 5 percent suggests that the model is accurate.

Table 4 demonstrates that Facebook has a significant coefficient of .6644197 when compared to other websites at the 1% level of significance (0.004). By inference, a one percent increase in Facebook usage by managers of small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs) in Kano state will lead to a one hundred sixty-six percent increase in the marketing effectiveness of SMEs in that state. This suggests that Facebook is the most effective platform to utilize if you want to engage with a large number of individuals at the same time. Even while Facebook is the most popular site for social networking, it also has a great deal of untapped potential for businesses. Because of the built-in performance measurement features, it is simple to monitor and assess how successful and well-liked an advertisement is on Facebook. This is made possible by Facebook advertisements. Once a company includes Facebook into their marketing strategy, they will have access to a number of helpful features on Facebook, two of the most advantageous of which are Facebook ads and business pages. As a result, the first null hypothesis, which stated that the Facebook platform does not have a substantial effect on the marketing efficacy of SMEs in Kano, is refuted by the findings of this study. The findings lent credence to the research conducted by

As can also be shown in Table 4, the coefficient for the Twitter platform (TWT) is .127917, and its p-value is 0.000. According to the p-value, which indicates a level of significance of 5 percent, it can be concluded that Twitter has a significant impact on MKTS. As a result, the findings of this investigation provide sufficient grounds for rejecting the second version of the study's null hypothesis. This study is also in agreement with a number of other studies, such as the ones conducted by Tubonimi, (2021); Masa'deh, et al (2021); and Ninette, (2019), all of which came to the conclusion that the use of the Twitter platform guarantees marketing effectiveness for a variety of different organizations. According to the authors, businesses are able to more quickly disseminate information and news through Twitter, which allows them to reach a vast audience online that follows the business. The writers also state that the use of Twitter can assist in positioning their brands, as well as acquire business insight through comments, which can raise their market knowledge and allow them to accurately target clients with relevant services and goods or improve business connections. This suggests that by utilizing Twitter as a social media platform, enhanced and direct marketing may be improved by making direct contact with the engaged audience on the network. On the other hand, YouTube (YT) has a coefficient of .2411195 and a p-value of 0.405, as seen in Table 4. It implies that YT has a negligible effect on MKTS at the 5% level of significance. The conclusion confirmed that the study did not uncover sufficient statistical evidence to reject null hypothesis three.

V. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The research was able to provide empirical proof that social media adoption have a significant impact on the marketing strategies used by SMEs in the state of Kano for period under reviewed. It has been demonstrated that social media platforms like Facebook and Twitter have a beneficial effect on the marketing efficiency of small and medium-sized businesses in the state of Kano. light of these findings, and conclusion, the study recommends that the management of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in the state of Kano should incorporate social media platforms like Facebook and Twitter into their marketing strategies and use these platforms extensively when providing customer service, As a result, their output will be enhanced.

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